

Revealing Hidden Emotions That Drive Brand Purchase: Implicit Priming Betters Explicit Self-Reports for a Frozen Food Brand

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Abstract: Recent research in neuroscience, psychology, and marketing confirms that emotions strongly, if not exclusively, drive people’s behavior, including their consumer behavior. Studies also show that people either can’t or won’t convey emotions that affect their behavior via explicit self-reports. Primarily to address deficiencies with explicit emotional self-reports, we used a priming technique to assess how targeted consumers’ implicitly felt about a well-known frozen food brand. The technique (which we call “Emotional Profiling”) revealed levels of discrete implicit emotions different from those conveyed by explicit emotional self-reports. Furthermore, none of the explicit emotions we measured significantly predicted the brand’s share of purchases, but two of the implicit emotions did. Additionally, our technique detected *discrete* implicit emotions, differentiating it from many common implicit techniques that only assess positive or negative feeling. In sum, the technique can help product designers and brand marketers find discrete implicit emotions that, when leveraged, can increase purchase.

Key words: *emotional research, implicit emotions, self-report, implicit priming.*

1. Introduction

If you are not a brand marketer, imagine that you are. Further imagine that you ask targeted consumers how your brand makes them feel. You record their responses verbatim or along a rating scale for each of a series of discrete emotions (e.g., happy, bored, and disgusted). Using this explicit self-report approach, do you think you’ll discover how they *really* feel about your brand? Assuming you also ask about their brand purchase, do you think you’ll discover the feelings that are most driving them to purchase your brand?

Answers to the fundamental question of how targeted consumers “feel” about brands are important to brand marketers. This is especially true lately, as research from neuroscience, psychology, and marketing convincingly reveals that emotions strongly, if not exclusively, drive our behavior, including our behavior as consumers. However, the importance of knowing how much and what specific emotions drive consumer behavior is teased by the fact that people often can’t or won’t explicitly convey their feelings about a brand, let alone which of their feelings most compel them to purchase the brand. Just asking someone how they feel about a brand often does not produce the whole emotional truth.

To address these two issues—that emotions are important to study and that people often can’t or won’t convey their true feelings—we developed an Emotional Profiling technique that was used to reveal how targeted consumers felt about a well-known frozen food brand.¹ Not only did the technique portray how the consumers explicitly felt about the brand, but more importantly, it revealed how they implicitly felt, too. Furthermore, the technique found implicit emotions that significantly predicted the brand’s purchase when explicit emotions did not. Finally, the technique improved upon other implicit assessment techniques (like Greenwald’s Implicit Association Test [1]) by making it practical to assess *multiple discrete emotions* vs. only bi-polar positive or negative feeling.

2. Rationale for This Study and Our Implicit Emotional Profiling Technique

2.1. Emotions Drive (Consumer) Behavior

Much recent research in neuroscience, psychology, and marketing has shown that emotions strongly, if not exclusively, drive people’s behavior, including their behavior as consumers. Although many before him have demonstrated emotions’ salience, Antonio Damasio has received much recent credit, particularly from his seminal book *Descartes’ Error* [2]. By carefully studying mentally ill patients, Damasio pinpointed decision-making deficiencies as damage to parts of the brain that connect reason and emotion. He concluded in this and a later book, *The Feeling of What Happens* [3], that decisions become dysfunctional when emotions do not inform them.

More recently, emotional researchers have provided corroborating evidence and conclusions. For instance, Frijda, Manstead, and Bem [4] wrote, “Although beliefs may guide our actions, they are not sufficient to initiate action. ...Emotions are prime candidates for turning a thinking being into an actor.” Daye and VanAuken [5] recognized that, “While people typically cite functional reasons for their purchases, study after study has shown that most purchase decisions are based on emotions.” Finally, in a particularly strong statement related to emotion in consumer behavior, O’Shaughnessy and O’Shaughnessy [6] wrote, “Emotion is not an aberrant element when making buying decisions, but a necessary condition if decisions are not to be continually postponed.”

In sum, emotions appear to be the dynamic that “turns thinking into behavior.”

2.2. People Often Can’t or Won’t Reveal Their Emotions

Accepting that emotions drive consumer behavior, we are challenged to understand *how* they do it. Gaining this understanding requires collecting data from consumers about their feelings related to their consumer behavior. But two data collection limitations exist. We call these limitations “unconscious” and “unwilling.” The unconscious limitation means that people often *can’t* reveal their emotions because their emotions operate in large part unconsciously—i.e., below their level of awareness. The unwilling limitation means that people often *won’t* reveal their emotions because doing so is often socially or culturally unacceptable. Collectively, these two emotional dynamics—unconscious and unwilling—are called “implicit.”

¹ The actual brand is not reported in this article to preserve confidentiality. However, knowing the actual brand is not important to what the study reveals.

Support for the “unconscious” limitation comes from many sources. Winkielman, Berridge, and Wilbarger [7] provided experimental evidence of emotions’ unconscious influence. They showed that thirsty respondents who were subliminally primed with happy faces evaluated a drink more positively and drank more of it than thirsty respondents who were subliminally primed with angry faces. Franzen and Bouwman [8] wrote, “We are not aware of most of our emotional reactions: we cannot ‘feel’ the emotion. Most of our emotional life takes place in the unconscious.” Zaltman [9] was quantitatively precise about the limitation: “According to most estimates, about 95 percent of thought, emotion, and learning occurs in the unconscious mind—that is, without our awareness.”

Support for the “unwilling” limitation also comes from many sources. For example, Wittenbrink [10] wrote that, “...Implicit measures promise to address a long-standing and fundamental problem with standard self-report measures of attitudes: people do not necessarily tell the truth when asked about their attitudes toward socially sensitive issues. Instead, people may report attitudes that they believe are more socially desirable in order to present themselves in a favorable way to others and to themselves.” Rapaille [11] positioned his comment in the context of traditional consumer research techniques: “When asked about their interests and preferences, [respondents] tend to give answers they believe the questioner wants to hear. This is because people respond with their cerebral cortexes, the part of the brain that controls intelligence, rather than emotion or instinct. Their answers are the product of deliberation. In most cases, however, they aren't saying what they feel.”

2.3. The Call for More Effective Implicit Emotional Assessment Techniques

Recognizing that these two limitations are not effectively addressed by many traditional market research techniques, researchers are calling for new implicit techniques. For instance, van Raaij and Ye [12] wrote, “Most conceptual and measurement approaches could be extended to less conscious processes and implicit (i.e., unconscious) learning. We expect that this will provide richer and more insightful explanations and conclusions. We need to employ new research methodology to collect data on automatic processing and implicit learning.” Cooper and Pawle [13] directly made the plea: “In review of the techniques available to measure emotion, our conclusion is that market research must allow for the measurement of both explicit conscious feelings and implicit cognitive emotions for a more comprehensive account of the consumer-brand relationship.” We’re not saying that explicit self-reports are useless. Obviously, people often can and will explicitly convey their true (consumer) emotions via self-reports. However, explicit self-reports can and do miss a great deal of people’s influential implicit emotions—the ones that are operating unconsciously or being guarded.

In addition to revealing influential implicit emotions, we wanted an Emotional Profiling technique that was more “emotion specific” than many other implicit techniques. Instead of assessing whether our targeted object (a frozen food brand) evoked just positive or negative feeling (like many commonly used implicit techniques do), we wanted to assess whether our frozen food brand evoked multiple discrete emotions, like happy, proud, guilty, and worried. Knowing this would improve strategic marketing recommendations to our brand’s executives.

Therefore, in addition to their explicit emotions, the Emotional Profiling technique we used was designed to assess targeted consumers’ discrete implicit emotions about a well-known frozen food brand. The discrete

emotions implicit assessment feature is what differentiates our technique from more traditional surveys that use explicit emotional self-reports and from other implicit assessment techniques that practically measure only bipolar positive or negative feeling.

2.4. The Implicit Assessment Feature of Our Emotional Profiling Technique

The implicit assessment feature of our Emotional Profiling technique was adapted from implicit measurement techniques widely used in social and cognitive psychology. These techniques involve activating implicit emotional associations with targeted objects and then asking respondents to complete an unrelated explicit task. Implicit emotional associations with the targeted objects disproportionately influence (i.e., “leak onto”) the explicit task responses.

Generally speaking, there are two types of implicit measurement techniques: 1) priming techniques, adapted largely from approaches credited to Fazio [14]; and 2) Implicit Association Test (IAT) techniques, adapted largely from approaches credited to Greenwald [1]. Both reveal “inner content” (e.g., attitudes, emotions, etc.) that are either unconscious (therefore, explicitly unavailable) or altered in explicit expression.

As previously mentioned, although useful in particular applications, IAT techniques posed practical limitations for our research. Specifically, adapting IAT techniques to build emotional profiles that consist of multiple discrete emotions required an impractically long procedure. Therefore, our approach was adapted from a particular priming technique (discussed below) more amenable to assessing multiple discrete emotions.

Priming techniques have consistently shown the ability to expose implicit content and to relate this content to behavior, including consumer behavior [14]. The Winkielman et al. study mentioned earlier [7] is one example. Also, using the technique that we adapted for this research, Payne, Govorun, and Arbuckle [15] showed that alcohol drinking behaviors were systematically related to implicit attitudes.

The technique we adapted for this study is called the Affective Misattribution Procedure (AMP), developed by Keith Payne and colleagues [16]. It is beyond the scope of this article to comprehensively discuss the genesis, procedures, and effectiveness of this technique; however, studies using the AMP have shown that implicit emotions can be detected and can, in some instances, predict behavior better than explicit emotions [15, 17, and 18]. Furthermore, addressing our secondary goal, the AMP has demonstrated the ability to assess multiple discrete emotions as opposed to just positive or negative emotion. For instance, Arbuckle [17] found the AMP to distinguish implicit feelings of fear, anger, and disgust and showed that those feelings related to different stereotypical images of African Americans. Furthermore, Conner [18] used an adapted AMP to show that implicit playfulness predicted college students’ preference for Samsung.

3. Our Emotional Profiling Study

3.1. Applications and Information Objectives

To substantiate our technique, our study intended to (1) assess discrete explicit and implicit emotions targeted respondents felt toward a well-known frozen food brand and (2) reveal discrete implicit emotions that could improve predictions of brand preference and/or purchase vs. discrete explicit emotions alone. By doing this, the technique intended to help this brand’s marketers **decide what emotions to activate to optimize their brand’s preference and/or purchase among their consumer target.**

To support this application, our study addressed the following questions:

- 1. Overall, does the consumer target feel more positive or more negative about the brand?**
- 2. What specific feelings does the consumer target have about the brand and how strong are those feelings?**
- 3. Are there important feelings that the consumer target has about the brand that are operating automatically, unconsciously, or are deliberately being hidden for some reason? If so, what are they?**
- 4. Which of these feelings is most impacting preference for or purchase of the brand among the consumer target?**

3.2. Method

To collect the data needed to support this study’s application and information objectives, moms with school-aged children (ages 6-13) who were responsible for preparing family meals were screened and recruited from a national consumer research panel (e-Rewards) to participate in an online “survey.” During the screening process, potential respondents were told that the study involved assessing “how well different visuals convey different feelings under different levels of distraction.” Once screened, potential respondents were directed to a website that administered the procedure online. When they got to the site, they received general instructions followed by questions pertaining to demographics. After the demographics, they engaged in two types of “feelings tasks”—implicit and explicit.

They first completed the implicit feelings task (IMP-FEEL). IMP-FEEL was adapted from Payne’s Affect Misattribution Procedure (AMP [16]).² Figure 1 presents the images and question asked across the IMP-FEEL task trials.³

² This task in this study was improved from a previous version [19] to obtain stronger internal reliability and to improve “structural fit,” which Payne et al. [20] had identified as an important consideration in previous AMPs.

³ Respondents did not see the images exactly this way, i.e., all three at once. The prime was shown first, followed by the symbol, emotion word, and question shown together.

Figure 1. IMP-FEEL task images and question.

IMP-FEEL involved 200 trials, each consisting of a “prime” event followed by a “symbol evaluation” event. The prime event involved quickly flashing either the brand name or a control image (a gray box only) on the screen for 200ms. The symbol evaluation event involved presenting the symbol and emotion word images together and asking the respondent, “Compared to designs like this in general, how much more or less does this design convey this feeling?” Respondents were given 5 seconds to answer along a 4-point scale—Much More, A Little More, A Little Less, or Much Less. The 200 trials consisted of each prime (brand and control) being paired with each emotion word (of which there were 10⁴) 10 times (2 x 10 x 10 = 200). Prime and symbol/emotion word pairings were randomly distributed across the 200 trials in eight blocks of 25 trials, with a short (respondent dictated) rest interval between each block.

Following IMP-FEEL, respondents completed the explicit feelings task (EXP-FEEL). The questions within this task, and the questions that followed, were positioned as “measurement control” questions. EXP-FEEL consisted of 20 questions. Each question involved presenting an image (either the brand name or the gray control box) and one of the 10 emotion words (the same words as in the IMP-FEEL task). Figure 2 generally presents how the images looked and the explicit question that was asked.

Figure 2. EXP-FEEL task images and question.

Once presented with the image and word, much like the IMP-FEEL questions, respondents were asked, “Compared to images like this in general, how much more or less does this image convey this feeling?” Respondents answered along a 4-point scale—Much More, A Little More, A Little Less, or Much Less. The 20

⁴ The emotion words, chosen together by the researcher and brand representatives, were good, comforted, happy, loving, proud, responsible, bad, bored, guilty, and worried.

questions consisted of pairing the frozen food brand name and the gray control box once with each of the 10 emotion words.

Following EXP-FEEL, respondents were asked the following questions about 5 frozen food brands: (1) their awareness of them; (2) the number of items they had purchased of each brand in the past 6 months; and (3) their rank-ordered preference for each of the brands⁵ in general, if recommending to a friend, for a family-size meal, and for a party-size meal.

The entire online session averaged about 20 minutes.

3.3. Analyses and Results

After eliminating data from non-qualified respondents,⁶ we analyzed data from 127 respondents in two phases—Emotional Profiling Analyses and Driver Analyses.

Emotional Profiling Analyses involved calculating and charting standardized implicit and explicit emotion scores for each of the 10 emotions and for the overall emotionality of the frozen food brand. Driver Analyses involved relating the Emotional Profiling emotion scores to brand preference and purchase to quantitatively examine which emotions most impacted these outcome measures.

Emotional Profiling Analyses. Emotion scores in the Emotional Profiling analyses were adjusted Cohen Ds, a commonly used statistic for standardizing emotion effects in these types of studies. Cohen Ds *for each implicit and explicit emotion* were calculated as follows:

1. For each respondent, we subtracted the control-associated emotion ratings (along the 4-point scale⁷) from the brand-associated emotion ratings to derive a single emotion score which represented how much more or less the emotion was evoked by the brand vs. the gray box (control) image.⁸
2. We then averaged each “brand-represented” emotion score across the respondents.
3. We then divided the averaged “brand-represented” emotion score by their standard deviation (giving us the emotion-specific Cohen D).
4. Finally, we multiplied these emotion-specific Cohen D scores by 100 for presentation purposes.

⁵ 1 = Most Preferred, 2 = Second Most Preferred, 3 = Third Most Preferred, 4 = Fourth Most Preferred, 5 = Least Preferred

⁶ Data from 41 respondents were eliminated due to data integrity issues – duplicate IDs, being unaware of the targeted brand, showing patterns of responding that strongly indicated they were just “going through the motions,” not paying attention to what was being asked of them (e.g., responding too quickly, responding with no variation, etc.).

⁷ Much More = +2, A Little More = +1, A Little Less = -1, Much Less = -2.

⁸ Since there were 10 trials for each of the emotions in the implicit task, we averaged the brand-primed emotion ratings and the control-primed emotion ratings before subtracting the control-primed emotion rating from the brand-primed emotion rating.

Figure 3 presents the Emotional Profiling chart for the frozen food brand. The standardized emotion scores are the adjusted Cohen Ds for each implicit and explicit emotion evoked by the frozen food brand.

Figure 3. Frozen Food Brand Emotional Profile among the Total Sample.

It's important to point out that since these are standardized scores, the "0" line running vertically through the chart indicates the point at which the brand prime/image evoked an emotional response equal to the control prime/image. In essence, a standardized emotion score of 0 represents a certain emotion being activated no more or less than its degree of activation in a neutrally-stimulated environment. Positive emotion scores indicate "higher than normal" emotional activation. Negative emotion scores indicate "lower than normal" emotional activation. Except for unusual circumstances, desired results are positive positive emotion scores and negative negative emotion scores.

The numbers on the chart need some clarification. (1) The numbers within the bars indicate the standardized Cohen D emotion scores calculated as described earlier, blue for implicit emotions and red for explicit emotions. (2) The numbers just to the right of the emotion words indicate the total degree to which that emotion was evoked by the brand. This is the addition of the implicit and explicit emotion scores. (3) The overall emotionality score is the addition of the average of the total individual positive emotion scores and the average of the total individual negative emotion scores (making sure that a negative negative emotion score is added within the equation).

Figure 3 shows several things. (1) The frozen food brand exhibited moderate to low emotionality, achieving an overall emotionality score of just 77. In a previous study, Conner [18] found overall emotionality scores of 119 and 80 for two brands of consumer electronics. (2) As in Conner's previous electronics brands study [18], explicit emotions were stronger than implicit emotions. We believe this has more to do with the more direct and conscious nature of the explicit task than to explicit emotions being more important. (3) Except for small effects for implicitly feeling guilty (+6), not loving (-5), and not comforted (-2) toward the brand, all emotions were in the desired direction. (4) The highest overall emotion score was for happy (+58), although comforted was the highest scoring explicit emotion (+52). (5) The lowest emotion score was for worried (-40).

Extending beyond the numbers in the chart, although there was a relatively high rank order correlation between the aggregated explicit and implicit feelings ($r = .58$), implicit and explicit feelings were not as correlated when examined on an individual respondent basis. When examined individually, the highest positive correlation between explicit and implicit emotions was $r = .15$ for responsible, while the highest negative correlation was $r = -.18$ for bored. These results indicate that implicit and explicit emotions were not synonymous and therefore worthy of examining as distinct phenomena.

Furthermore, increasing the number of implicit brand prime/emotion word repetitions from 5 in Conner’s electronics study [18] to 10 in this study helped us achieve acceptable reliability. Cronbach alphas for each of the implicit brand-primed emotions ranged from .661 to .750, averaging .721.

Driver Analyses. Although these emotion scores are interesting and potentially useful, they are not highly actionable by themselves. Since purchase is the ultimate goal of marketing, the more actionable question arises, “Which of the emotions most predict purchase?” Purchase being the key outcome measure, we constructed a chart that resulted from comparing the emotion scores of respondents with relatively high shares of purchases for this brand (35% +, $N = 52$) to those with relatively low shares of purchases (< 35%, $N = 51$). Once divided into these groups, we subtracted the standardized (Cohen D) emotion scores of the lower shares group from the standardized (Cohen D) emotion scores of the higher shares group for each emotion. The result was a chart of standardized emotion scores representing emotions that were related to higher shares of purchases for the brand. Figure 4 presents that chart.

Figure 4. Frozen Food Brand Emotional Profile Among Those With Higher vs. Lower Share of Purchases.

Figure 4 clearly shows that feeling implicitly loving and happy were the two emotions most associated with higher shares of purchases for this brand.⁹

This descriptive driver analysis was a start. For a more precise examination of which emotions most predicted preference and purchase of this brand, we also conducted a series of multiple regression analyses. The results of these analyses appear in Tables 1-3.

⁹ This descriptive result is highlighted in yellow because it was further supported by the multiple regression results that follow in the next three tables.

Table 1. Frozen Food Brand Multiple Regression Results – Explicit Emotions Only as Predictors

Outcome Variables	R²/p	Significant Betas
General Preference	.086/.010	xGood -.213; xGuilty -.191
Recommend Preference	.063/.010	xGood -.250
Family-Size Meal Preference	.110/.003	xWorried .252; xResponsible -.239
Party-Size Meal Preference	.103/.004	xWorried .269; xResponsible -.200
Share of Purchases (6 mo.)	<i>No significant predictors</i>	

Table 1 shows the results when only the explicit emotion scores were included as predictor variables. The table shows that (1) feeling explicitly good, responsible, and, interestingly, guilty significantly predicted higher preference for the frozen food brand;¹⁰ (2) feeling explicitly worried significantly predicted lower preference; and (3) none of the explicit emotions significantly predicted share of purchases.

Table 2. Frozen Food Brand Multiple Regression Results – Implicit Emotions Only as Predictors

Outcome Variables	R²/p	Significant Betas
General Preference	<i>No significant predictors</i>	
Recommend Preference	<i>No significant predictors</i>	
Family-Size Meal Preference	<i>No significant predictors</i>	
Party-Size Meal Preference	.034/.037	iResponsible -.185
Share of Purchases (6 mo.)	.041/.039	iLoving .203

Table 2 shows these results when only the implicit emotion scores were included as predictor variables. The table shows that (1) feeling implicitly responsible significantly predicted higher preference for this brand's party-size meals; and (2) feeling implicitly loving significantly predicted share of purchases.

Table 3. Frozen Food Brand Multiple Regression Results – Explicit and Implicit Emotions as Predictors

Outcome Variables	R²/p	Significant Betas
General Preference	.136/.002	xGood -.242; iLoving -.236; xBored -.201
Recommend Preference	.154/.001	xGood -.230; iProud -.230; iLoving -.227
Family-Size Meal Preference	.110/.003	xWorried .252; xResponsible -.239
Party-Size Meal Preference	.103/.004	xWorried .269; xResponsible -.200
Share of Purchases (6 mo.)	.110/.009	iLoving .260; iHappy .219

Table 3 shows these results when both the explicit and implicit emotion scores were included as predictor variables. The table shows that (1) a wide variety of emotions, explicit and implicit, significantly (and somewhat confusingly) predicted higher preference; however, (2) only implicitly feeling loving and happy significantly predicted the more important outcome variable, share of purchases. Emphasizing the second point, *without the implicit technique, we would have not found emotions that predicted purchase of this brand.*

¹⁰ Negative betas for preference outcome variables indicate a relationship with emotion in the same direction because higher emotion scores mean more of the emotion, but lower absolute preference ranks mean higher preference. The opposite is true for positive betas.

One issue with this study was that respondents were allowed 5 seconds to respond to each implicit trial, which is about 3 seconds longer than had typically been allowed in past AMP studies. We allowed this extra time because we asked the implicit question in a new way and several respondents in pretesting became frustrated with having to answer so quickly. Upon seeing relatively weak implicit emotion scores, we wondered whether conscious deliberation began to enter and mask a true implicit effect. To check this, we re-examined the data only for respondents whose average implicit task trial was between 1 and 2 seconds ($N = 83$). From this we found (1) a small, but consistent, increase in the implicit emotion scores (+7 on average); (2) very little change in explicit emotion scores, and, perhaps most importantly; (3) within the implicit and explicit predictors model, a stronger positive impact of implicit loving on share of sales ($\beta = .302$) with no significant impact for any other implicit or explicit emotion.

3.4. Conclusion

The results of our study met our primary and secondary objectives. They showed that (1) our technique could detect and distinguish a variety of feelings for this frozen food brand; (2) implicit emotions can be different than explicit emotions; (3) implicit emotions can predict desirable outcomes, in this case higher share of purchases; (4) explicit emotional self-reports can be insufficient, if not inaccurate, in predicting desirable outcomes, in this case higher share of purchases; and (5) our technique can provide more specific marketing direction than many other implicit techniques by revealing multiple discrete emotions that drive purchase—specifically for this brand, implicitly feeling loving and, to a lesser degree, happy.

4. Discussion

With the abundance of recent emotion research in neuroscience, psychology, and marketing, there can be little doubt that emotions play an important, if not necessary and paramount, role in driving consumer behavior. Accepting this, if brand marketers' ultimate goal is to increase targeted consumers' purchase of their products and services (which it should be), emotions should be effectively studied. Because emotions affect behavior in large part implicitly, effectively assessing emotions means having to use implicit emotional assessment techniques. Many such techniques exist, including indirect psychotherapeutic dialog (e.g., projectives, psychodrama, and metaphor elicitation) and psychophysiological measurement (e.g., brain scanning, skin conductance, and facial muscle movement). Implicit association or misattribution techniques also provide effective ways to reveal implicit emotions that drive consumer behavior. Our discrete implicit Emotional Profiling technique is one of these, improving upon traditional explicit emotional self-reports, as well as many implicit techniques that only assess bi-polar positive or negative emotions. Using this technique can help brand and product marketers develop more emotional-engaging brands, products, and services by revealing compelling hidden emotions that drive their purchase.

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